

Chemical Constituents of Stem Bark of *Mangifera indica* Linn. (Cultivar *Desi*)

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The structure of mangdesisterol, mangfarnasoic acid and mangedesmenone, isolated from the stem bark of *Mangifera indica* variety *Desi*, are reported along with characterisation of some minor constituents.

The stem bark of *Mangifera indica* Linn. is reported useful for the cure of various diseases in the indigenous medicine¹. In continuation our interest in the chemistry of the stem bark of the plant², we now report the structures of three new chemical constituents along with some known compounds isolated from the *M. indica* Linn. (cultivar *Desi*).

Results and Discussion

The ethanolic extract of the stem bark of *M. indica* on column chromatography afforded three new and five known compounds. The structures of the unknown constituents have been elucidated by spectral data and chemical reactions. The structures of the known compounds, namely 3 β ,22-dihydroxycycloart-24*E*-en-26-oic acid (1), 3 α ,27-dihydroxycycloart-24*E*-en-26-oic acid (7), n-triacontane (8), n-hexacontane (9) and taraxerol (10) have been established directly by comparing melting points, derivatisation and chromatographic results.

Mangdesisterol (2) : Compound 2 was obtained as colourless crystalline product, m.p. 110–12^o, C₂₉H₄₈O₂ (*M*⁺, 426), responding positive to Liebermann-Buchard reaction, $\nu_{\max}$ 3405 (OH), 1705 (C=O) and 1625, 1560 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation); *m/z* 411 [*M*-Me]⁺, 408 [*M*-H₂O]⁺, 383 [*M*-43]⁺, 341 [*M*-85, ion *b*]⁺, 314 [*M*-112, ion *d*]⁺, 300 [*M*-126, ion *f*]⁺, 262 [*M*-164, ion *h*]⁺, 234 [*M*-192, ion *j*]⁺ and 192 [ion *i*]⁺, suggesting³ that it was a C₂₉-sterol possessing one double bond in the carbocyclic system. The ion fragments at *m/z*

85, 341 [ions *a, b*]⁺, 112, 314 [ions *c, d*]⁺, 126, 300 [ions *e, f*]⁺ and 164, 262 [ions *g, h*]⁺, suggested the location of the hydroxyl group at C-3 and position of double bond⁴ at C₇-C₈. The ion fragments at *m/z* 285 [*M*-side chain, 141]⁺, 271 [*M*-SC-Me]⁺, 256 [271-Me]⁺ and 242 [*M*-SC, ring C fusion]⁺ showed the presence of a C₁₀ side-chain containing an ethyl group. On the basis of biogenetic as well as close similarities in chemical shifts of the protons of the side-chain in related compounds^{4,5} the ethyl group was placed at C-24. The ionic peaks at *m/z* 164, 262 [ions *g, h*]⁺ and 192, 234 [ions *i, j*]⁺ were suggestive of the presence of the carbonyl group at C-11.

The ¹H nmr spectrum of 2 exhibited the presence of a one-proton signal at δ 5.10 assigned to C-7. A one-proton broad multiplet at δ 3.23 with half-width of 15.5 Hz could be reconciled with the α -proton at C-3. The signals for six methyl groups appeared in the upfield region at δ 1.20–0.76. It gave a monoacetyl derivative (3) showing the presence of a secondary hydroxyl group ($\nu_{\max}$ 1725 cm⁻¹). On the basis of these evidences the structure of mangdesisterol (2) was established as 24-ethylcholesta-7-en-3 β -ol-12-one.

Mangfarnasoic acid (4) : Compound 4, m.p. 183–85^o, C₁₅H₃₀O₂ (*M*⁺, 242), produced effervescence with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution suggesting the presence of carboxylic group which was also supported by preparation of its methyl ester (5). Its ir spectrum showed bands for COOH

at 3365 and 1680 cm^{-1} which is evidenced by the mass spectral peak at m/z 198 ($M-44$). The ion fragments at m/z 183, 169 and 155

appear due to successive elimination of methyl functionalities from 198 mass unit. The appearance of the base peak at m/z 73 [ion b] $^+$ and a peak at 169 [ion a] $^+$ confirmed the existence of the carboxylic group at one of the terminal positions. The other ion fragments at m/z 127 [ion g] $^+$, 115 [ion h] $^+$, 143 [ion j] $^+$, 99 [ion i] $^+$, 185 [ion p] $^+$ and 57 [ion o] $^+$ suggested the compound to be an acyclic farnasane-like sesquiterpene possessing terminal carboxylic function.

^1H nmr spectrum of 4 exhibited the presence of methyl groups at δ 1.06 (Me), 0.76 (2 $\times$ Me) and 0.70 (Me). Absence of any signal in the range δ 1.50–9.0 ruled out the presence of primary and secondary carbinol protons and exocyclic or trisubstituted double bond in the molecule. These evidences led us to elucidate the structure of 4 as farnasan-1-oic acid.

Mangeudesmenone (6) : Compound 6, m.p 140–42 $^\circ$, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$ (M^+ , 236), has four double bond equivalents. Its ir spectrum showed bands at 3380 (OH), 1615 (unsaturation) and 1705 cm^{-1} (a six-membered ketonic group). A bicyclic nature of the sesquiterpene was suggested in which two double bond equivalents are adjusted in two rings, one in carbon-carbon double bond and the fourth one in the ketonic function. Its uv absorption maxima at 221, 255 and 275 nm revealed the presence of extended conjugation in the molecule. ^1H nmr spectrum of 6 displayed two downfield broad singlets, one proton each, at δ 6.60 and 5.23 (H-1 and H-2, respectively), two three-proton singlets at δ 1.00 and 0.96 (Me-15 and Me-11, respectively) and a six-proton singlet at δ 0.86 (Me-13 and Me-14 protons). The appearance of the typical angular C-15 methyl signal at δ 1.00 showed eudesmane type carbon framework of the sesquiterpene. EIMS of 6 exhibited typical ion fragments at m/z 221 [$M-\text{Me}$] $^+$, 218 [$M-\text{H}_2\text{O}$] $^+$, 206 [$M-2 \times \text{Me}$] $^+$, 177 [$M-\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{O}$] $^+$, 154 [ion a] $^+$, 82 [ion b] $^+$, 122 [ion d] $^+$ and 114 [ion e] $^+$.

Compound 6 did not react with acetic anhydride-pyridine showing the tertiary nature of the hydroxyl function. On the basis of these evidences the structure of mangeudesmenone was assigned as eudesm-1(2)-en-3-on-12-ol (6).

Phytochemical studies of the stem bark of *M. indica* cultivar *Desi* revealed that the constituents 3 β ,22-dihydroxycycloart-24*E*-en-26-oic acid, 3 α ,27-dihydroxycycloart-24*E*-en-26-oic acid and taraxerol occurred in the stem barks of the varieties *Banganpalli* or *Neelum*^{6,7}. The presence of sesquiterpenoids has been reported for the first time in the mango bark.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) were recorded on a 60 MHz instruments using TMS as internal reference and electron impact mass spectra (EIMS) on a Jeol double beam instrument (70 eV). Silica gel (Qualigen) for column (60–120 mesh) and tlc were used. Tlc solvent systems were petrol-C₆H₆ (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3), C₆H₆, C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (1:1, 1:2), CHCl₃ and CHCl₃-MeOH (1.5:0.5). Iodine vapour, perchloric acid, ceric ammonium sulphate and uv-light were used for visualisation of tlc spots.

Extraction : The dried and pulverised bark (2.2 kg), collected from the mango orchards of Mehrauli, New Delhi, in September 1991, was extracted with ethanol in a Soxhlet apparatus. The dark brown concentrated extract (380 g) was adsorbed on to a small portion of silica gel. The dried slurry was chromatographed over silica gel column and successively eluted with petroleum ether, CHCl₃ and MeOH mixtures in order of increasing polarity to get the following compounds.

Mangdesisterol (2) : Fractions obtained on elution of the column with CHCl₃-MeOH (1:1) furnished a colourless compound (2), m.p. 110–12°, found homogenous by tlc (CHCl₃-MeOH, 9:1), $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 215 and 275 nm (log ϵ 8.2 and 2.1); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 405, 2 920, 2 855, 1 705, 1 625, 1 560, 1 535, 1 505, 1 465, 1 255, 1 029, and 803 cm⁻¹; δ 5.10 (1H, m, H-7), 3.23 (1H, br m, W_{1/2} 15.5 Hz, H-3 α), 2.46 (2H, s, CH₂-12), 1.20 (3H, s, Me-19), 0.93 (6H, s, Me-21, Me-29), 0.83 (6H, s, Me-26, Me-27), 0.76 (3H, s, Me-18); *m/z* (rel. int.) 426 *M*⁺ (C₂₉H₄₈O₂) (2.1), 411 (3.8), 408 (1.8), 383 (2.2), 341 (3.1), 330 (3.4), 314 (8.6), 304 (5.2), 285 (3.1), 271 (1.1), 262

(1.1), 256 (8.9), 242 (3.1), 233 (3.0), 228 (3.2), 218 (37.2), 192 (4.1), 164 (12.5), 126 (70.2), 112 (13.1), 95 (50.1), 82 (40.6), 69 (58.2), 55 (91.2), 43 (100). Treatment of 2 with acetic anhydride and pyridine yielded a monoacetyl derivative (mangdesisterol acetate; 3), $\nu_{\max}$ 1725 cm⁻¹.

Mangfarnasoic acid (4) : Further elution of the column with a mixture of CHCl₃-MeOH (1:9) gave colourless crystals of mangfarnasoic acid (4), m.p. 183–85°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 365, 2 925, 2 550, 1 680, 1 570, 1 445, 1 395, 1 265, 1 075, 786 and 745 cm⁻¹; δ 1.50 (1H, m, CH), 1.40 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.20 (14H, br s, 7 $\times$ CH₂), 1.06 (3H, br s, CH₃), 0.76 (6H, s, 2 $\times$ CH₃), 0.70 (3H, br s, CH₃); *m/z* (rel. int.) 242 [*M*]⁺ (C₁₅H₃₀O₂) (0.5), 198 (13.1), 185 (1.1), 183 (1.1), 171 (2.0), 169 (19.8), 157 (0.1), 155 (14.2), 153 (50.2), 143 (2.1), 141 (0.8), 127 (3.1), 123 (22.4), 115 (4.8), 101 (9.1), 99 (8.4), 97 (29.6), 87 (13.2), 85 (18.2), 73 (100), 71 (37.8), 57 (64.8), 45 (35.6), 43 (79.2). Treatment of mangfarnasoic acid (4; 10 mg) with diazomethane in solvent ether (5 ml) yielded a monomethyl derivative (5), $\nu_{\max}$ 1 730 cm⁻¹.

Mangedesmenone (6) : Fractions obtained on eluting the column with methanol gave a light pink coloured compound (6), m.p. 140–42°; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 221, 255, 275 nm (log ϵ 6.5, 3, 3); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 380, 1 705, 1 615, 1 520, 1 450, 1 220, 1 030, 815 and 765 cm⁻¹; δ 6.60 (1H, br s, H-2), 5.23 (1H, br s, H-1), 1.26 (6H, br s, 3 $\times$ CH₂), 1.00 (3H, s, Me-15), 0.96 (3H, s, Me-11), 0.86 (6H, s, Me-13, Me-14); *m/z* (rel. int.) 236 [*M*]⁺ (C₁₅H₂₄O₂) (1.1), 221 (1.1), 218 (17.3), 206 (4.2), 177 (1.1), 175 (2.1), 160 (2.1), 153 (11.2), 122 (8.9), 114 (2.1), 107 (29.1), 85 (99.1), 83 (98.2), 61 (58.9), 43 (100).

3 β ,22-Dihydroxycycloart-24*E*-en-26-oic acid (1) : Elution of the column with CHCl₃-MeOH (1:1) yielded colourless crystals of 3 β ,22-dihydroxycycloart-24*E*-en-26-oic acid (1), crystallised from CHCl₃, m.p. 219–22° (lit.⁷ 220–23°).

3 α ,27-Dihydroxycycloart-24*E*-en-26-oic acid (7) : Further elution of the column with pure MeOH afforded colourless crystals of 7, m.p. 207–09° (lit.⁷ 205–07°).

n-Triacontane (8) : Fractions obtained with petroleum ether on crystallisation from CHCl₃-MeOH (3 : 1) afforded colourless crystals of *n*-triacontane (8), found homogenous by tlc (C₆H₆), m.p. 65–66° (lit. 66°).

n-Hexacontane (9) : Elution of the column with petrol-CHCl₃ (4 : 1) on crystallisation with CHCl₃-MeOH (3 : 1) frunished colourless crystals of *n*-hexacontane (9), found homogenous by tlc (C₆H₆-CHCl₃, 1 : 1), m.p. 98–99° (lit. 99°).

Taraxerol (10) : Further elution of the column with CHCl₃-MeOH (1 : 3) afforded colourless flakes of taraxerol (10). crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH (1 : 1) m.p. 282–85° (lit. 282–85°); λ_{max} (MeOH) 210, 215, 220, 222 nm (log ε 8.7, 6.2, 3.1, 1.5); acetate derivative, m.p. 303–04°.

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